

HISTORICAL AND ARCHEOLOGICAL SCIENCES

AT THE BEGINNING OF WORLD WAR II BAKU OIL IN THE MILITARY-POLITICAL PLANS OF THE BRITISH AND FRENCH STATES

Hasanova A.

PhD Candidate

Azerbaijan University of Languages

Abstract

The article examines the plan to destroy the Baku oil fields by Great Britain and France during World War II. The main object of the study is the secret plans developed by Great Britain and France to prevent Baku oil from falling into the hands of the Germans. At the same time, the issue of reconnaissance flights over Baku by the Allied air forces and the possibility of military air attacks is also examined.

Keywords: oil, bombing, plan, war, ally.

The Molotov-Ribbentrop Pact signed between Germany and the USSR in 1941 on "non-aggression" made Hitler and Stalin allies. This alliance posed a threat as the prospect of the USSR supplying Germany with fuel.

After the 1939 agreement, Germany began to import oil from the Soviets. In 1940, 626 thousand (approximately 1/3 of all German imports); at the beginning of 1941, 258 thousand tons of oil were imported. This oil mainly came from the Caucasus. During the 18-month period during which the agreement was in force, Germany received a total of 911,000 tons of oil from the Soviets. It was thanks to this oil that Germany was able to significantly finance the 1939-1941 campaign. According to S. Karl, the 1939 economic agreement with the USSR allowed Germany to obtain the necessary materials, especially oil, iron, etc., to prepare for the upcoming war. Before the war, Germany covered only 33% of its domestic needs. Without Soviet imported oil, the German military machine could not wage war for a long time.

Since the summer of 1939, the USSR, in alliance with Germany, occupied eastern Poland, attacked Finland, and supplied Germany with oil and raw materials. The risk of the Red Army being drawn into a direct war against the Western powers and the quickly ending Western campaign prevented the fulfillment of this obligation.

The planned strikes by the French and British on the Baku oil fields would have caused no less problems for the USSR, if not more, than if the Germans had attacked from the West. If Baku oil were lost, the USSR would become an immobile giant, its economy and armed forces would be paralyzed. This could lead to complete chaos and loss of control over a huge area. On February 22, 1940, General Gamelin wrote in his report to the French Prime Minister that "the oil shortage that would arise as a result of the bombing of Baku would paralyze the Red Army and the Soviet Air Force, cause famine and even lead to the collapse of the Soviet Union." Thus, the main weakness of the Russian economy is its dependence on Caucasian oil. Both its armed forces and mechanized agriculture are completely dependent on this source. More than 90% of oil production and 80% of oil refining are concentrated in the

Caucasus (mainly in Baku). Therefore, any serious interruption in oil supplies would have long-term consequences and could even lead to the collapse of Russia's military, industrial and agricultural systems.

The strategic bombing plan for the Soviet oil fields in the Caucasus (the oil industry in Azerbaijan), developed by the Anglo-French troops in the summer of 1940, was called "Operation Pike".

Why "Pike"? In the summer of 1918, the British sent a force of about a thousand soldiers to Baku under the command of General Dunsterville. However, as a result of the capture of the city by the Ottoman army on September 15, they hurriedly left Baku, and at that time the British suffered losses in a skirmish with the attacking Turks. Among the dead was a colonel named Pike. Dunsterville had sent him to Tbilisi as his representative during the occupation of Baku. Some of those who captured Baku in 1918 and led this operation were still working in the British Ministry of War in 1940, and some of them remembered the brave colonel. That is why the second march on Baku was called "Pike".

The British military planning for this initiative took place in the first year of World War II, when the Soviet Union, through the Hitler-Stalin Pact, had become an ally of Hitler's Germany, at least in the division of Eastern Europe and also in armaments. The strategic objective of the planned military air strikes was to destroy the Soviet oil industry, centered in Baku, in order to reduce the mobility of the Red Army and cause the possible collapse of the Soviet economy. The operation was also intended to deny Germany access to Soviet resources.

This operation was led by the commander of the British Air Force, John Slessor. Planning began in December 1939. The date of execution of the operation was set for May 15, 1940. The British gentlemen were preparing to bomb Baku both at night and during the day. For this purpose, they also intended to use night bomber aircraft.

In April 1940, six French and three British bomber squadrons began moving towards Syria and Mosul in Iraq. On 17 April 1940, Maxime Weygand reported to Maurice Gamelin that preparations for the bombing of the Caucasus oil fields were so advanced that the operation could begin in late June or early July. British aircraft under the command of Sydney Cotton took aerial

photographs of the oil fields over Baku and Batumi in March and April 1940. 117 Farman F. 221, Martin Maryland and Vickers Wellington aircraft were to be used. These aircraft were equipped with stereoscopic cameras capable of taking pictures from a height. They were equipped with additional tanks and were to drop 324 tons of bombs on Batumi, Poti, Grozny and Baku within 10–45 days. According to French calculations, 360 group flights were to be carried out to destroy a total of 120 oil refining complexes. As a result of the air raid, Baku was to be razed to the ground in 15 days, Grozny in 12, and Batumi in 1 day. French diplomat Rene Massigli reported to Paris that US oil engineers "observed that the ground was so saturated with oil as a result of the exploitation of oil fields that the fire could immediately spread to the sea. It would take months to extinguish the entire neighboring region and years to resume work." On January 25, 1941, the German ambassador to Moscow, Friedrich Werner, warned the head of the Soviet government and Foreign Minister Vyacheslav Mikhailovich Molotov against the British-French movement in the Caucasus. On June 16, 1940, the 9th German Panzer Division seized a train at the station in the small town of La Charité. The train contained boxes containing a large number of secret documents taken from the French General Staff. These included files related to Operation Pike. Goebbels wrote about this in his diary on July 3, 1940: "A corporal in France has made a great discovery and found the protocol of all the secret negotiations between Paris and London. It is a great discovery. We will publish the materials in La Charite. They are destructive materials." After a group of experts confirmed its authenticity, the plan was presented to the public by the German press on July 3, 1940 as a sensational discovery. Its main sensation was the plan of London and Paris to bomb Baku and attack the Caucasus. On July 4, the Germans published excerpts from the documents they had captured. This saved Germany and other states, including the USSR, from being drawn into chaos by the trickery of the Allies. Germany took timely countermeasures against this plan and quickly crushed France. Hitler gave information about this plan in his speech in the Reichstag on July 19, 1940. The documents were published in "White Paper No. 6." A copy of the documents is presented to a TASS correspondent. The newspaper Pravda publishes extensive materials based on the White Book.

Hermann Goering, in his testimony at the Nuremberg Trials, stated that Rovel's command, together with long-range reconnaissance units, had observed the gathering of French and British aircraft squadrons in Syria for Operation Pike.

In October 1940, the British ambassador to Moscow, Richard Stafford Cripps, offered Soviet Foreign Minister Molotov a "quid pro quo" (an agreement in which goods or services are exchanged between two or more parties; something given to a person in exchange

for a job done) in exchange for the Soviet Union's neutrality in the German-British war. One of the points of the British "quid pro quo" was to abandon military operations against Baku and Batumi.

When preparations for the operation were entering the final stage, aircraft and crews were already beginning to be deployed to airfields when Hitler attacked France. A month before the start of the operation, on May 10, 1940, France was occupied by Germany.

In June 1940, the Anglo-French alliance was defeated by the Nazis in the defense of Norway. As a result, the London government recalled the air units that were ready to bomb Baku. At the same time, France fell under the occupation of the Nazis. The French signed a humiliating agreement on June 22 and were crushed, deprived of their army and most of their territory. After June 22, 1941, Moscow and London became allies in the fight against Nazism.

The strategic "Pike" operation, which had been prepared for months by the states that wanted to burn Baku, failed for weeks and even days as a result of the battles that took place during the war. Lord Alan Patrick Herbert, a British MP, poet-satirist and himself a naval officer, knew from personal experience what a real war was and at that time ridiculed the plan to bomb Baku with his poem "Baku or the Card Game". Thus, as the poet Herbert noted in his poem, the plan for the bombing of Baku remained on the map. After the invasion of the Soviet Union by Nazi Germany in Operation Barbarossa in June 1941, the "Pike" plan was restored, replaced by the name "Raspberry", as a contingency plan to be used in the event that German forces captured the Caucasian oil fields.

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